

Travel Service Monopoly through Satisfaction and Loyalty: A Case of Starline Paribahan (Pvt.) Limited, Bangladesh

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Abstract

Continuous improvements of passenger travelling services ensure passenger well-being. For significant transformative changes in end-to-end travel journey, it is necessary to know passenger desires and preferences. It also depends on care about the passengers, accessibility, cleanliness, staff hospitality, safe journey, and so on. Though there are many transport services available both direct and local services on the way of Feni to Chittagong, but passengers' choices are varied with influence of the factors like quality service, one stop service, waiting time, price, income, brand belief. The fact comes to reality keeping faith on brand with anonymous flexibility that exceeding the most common consideration for selecting a transport service from earlier research. Depending on the relationships, hypotheses were set both for loyalty and satisfaction in relation to brand belief, income, quality service, waiting time and one stop service and strongly supported, with path coefficients effectively. This justification finally indicates the new mood of loyalty of passengers toward passenger travelling services in the region and creates abundant scope for domination in service.

Key words: Travel Service, Satisfaction, Loyalty, Structural Equation Modeling.

Introduction

Passenger travelling services of Bangladesh is historically facing challenges from its inception. It is also being blamed for non-consistency of services in the long run. In some cases, safety and security issues are arisen but competition makes them up to the mark. Desired service expectation is worked for being customers happy and worked as a-heading factor against competitors (Davidow and Uttal, 1998). However, the general quality of services at all levels and by all modes have been poor along with unreliable service operations and safety & security issues (Mahmud. Rahman and Hasanat-E- Rabbi, 2012).

Feni, a small and populated district located in the south-eastern part of Bangladesh, is bounded by Comilla district on the north, Chittagong district and the Bay of Bengal to the south, Tripura (Indian State) and Chittagong district to the east and Noakhali district to the west (Banglapedia). That's why passengers are always remain vigilant & traveling from Chittagong to Feni and Feni to Chittagong. On the way of Feni to Chittagong and vice-versa, there are a number of transport

services available which can be categorized as (i) Direct service without Stoppage at Feni, (ii) Direct service with stoppage at Feni and (iii) Local services. Starline is considered to be one of the oldest service providers in this region particularly on passenger travelling services in Feni region and getting excessive preferences from passengers for quality service and belief. The most considerate gap between Starline and other services are using common factors like one stop service, waiting time, income as well. These preferences have been accelerating the path way of Starline in a monopoly nature. That's why; the study aims to identify the substantial factors of passenger in travelling from Feni to Chittagong and contribution of each factor construct on loyalty and satisfaction toward the transport services in this region.

Income, Price & Quality Service

Quality service is a burning issue for service-oriented industry. Service Companies particularly on transport, the brand/company needs to match resources to the demand by evaluating relationships among the nature of demand, the capacity requirement and related risk measures (Heskett, Sasser & Hart, 1990). By increasing facilities and capacity, it is possible to meet the increased demand in transportation system adopting "supply side" strategies (Wilson & Shirazi, 1991). Transport prices can be structured in various ways and price structures are affected through the consumer responses like perceived cost structures, perceived fairness, attitudes, distances, age and gender (Bonsall, Dix, Stone, and Stewart, 2006); trip types, distances and users (Dargay, 2010); transport modes, and travel time (Small & Winston, 1999); population size & income (Burt & Hoover, 2006), transport and travel cost, fuel price (Buehler, 2010), household demographics, and location (Whelan, 2007); vehicle types & traveling options (Giuliano and Dargay, 2006) and socioeconomic factors and travel conditions (Karlaftis and Golias, 2002). Finally, to evaluate the travel and transport impacts, distance, real household income, age of head of household, number of children or family tour, employment status, occupational class, availability of transport, and density are worth considerable (Santos, McGuckin, Nakamoto, Gray, & Liss, 2011).

Service quality is addressed with expectation and perceptions of service (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry, 1985) whereas the monetary price and the nonmonetary price particularly on time, search, and psychological costs would be considered under perceived price (Zeithaml, 1988; Dodds, Monroe, and Grewal, 1991). However, price is a strong factor limiting the buying power or consumer choices and preference for price sensitive consumers. Discomfort, time of travel and risk are considerable factor for transport prices though changes in price affected through location decisions, vehicle type, type of service selected, frequency of (Litman, 2013). The earlier resulting statistics of May, Grant-Muller, Marsden, and Thanos (2008) tend to overlook or undercount off-

peak travel, short trips, poor people's travel, children's travel, and non-motorized travel under the dimension of quality service in survey, but Rystam (1998) suggested counting hard standard factors like travelling time, fare etc. and soft standard factors like comfort, information etc; the objective factors for transport services like gender, age, and trips related factors especially purpose and subjective factors like valuations of the alternative's characteristics, attitudes and lifestyle. These factors are based on the individual's perceptions and are often more difficult to quantify. Finally, the transport related attributes that better describe the travel standard are timetable, comfort and service factors, and quality satisfaction and safety (Kottenhoff, 1999). Consequently, this study hypothesizes that income, quality service, and price are significant predictors for both satisfaction and loyalty.

Hypothesis 1: Income (I) has a positive effect on satisfaction;

Hypothesis 2: Income (I) has a positive effect on loyalty;

Hypothesis 3: Price (P) has a positive effect on satisfaction;

Hypothesis 4: Price (P) has a positive effect on loyalty;

Hypothesis 5: Quality Service (QS) has a positive effect on satisfaction;

Hypothesis 6: Quality Service (QS) has a positive effect on loyalty.

Brand Belief

Trust that lead to a higher level of loyalty (Morgan & Hunt, 1994) is based on the belief that guided to and motivated for favorable and positive intentions toward the welfare and interests of the object (Ballester and Aleman, 2001). True brand loyalty not only repeats purchasing behavior but also commits to brands through psychological and evaluative decision-making approach (Bloemer and Kasper, 1995). Customer satisfaction is treated as one of the most frequently used indicators to measure the success of a marketing strategy depending on customer trust perception (Flavian, Martinez, and Polo, 2001) where brand focuses mental image of the consumer with symbolic meanings that associated with the specific attributes of a product or service (Cretu & Brodie, 2007; Dobni & Zinkhan, 1990). More specifically, customer loyalty is the degree to which the customer has exhibited repurchasing behavior of a particular company service and the significance of expenditure on that particular type of service (Hellier, 2003). As a result, this study hypothesizes that brand belief is a significant predictor for both satisfaction and loyalty.

Hypothesis 7: Brand Belief (BrB) has a positive effect on satisfaction;

Hypothesis 8: Brand Belief (BrB) has a positive effect on loyalty.

One Stop Service and Waiting Time

A deeply held commitment to re-buy or re-patronize a preferred product/service might cause repetitive same-brand or same brand set purchasing despite of situational influences. But marketing efforts had the potential to cause switching behavior (Oliver, 1997) and made the psychological attachment to a service (Beatty, Kahle, and Homer, 1988). One stop service is the preferential service for loyal passengers for reaching destination in-time. This service basically differentiates the local and direct services in passenger travelling services where no passenger should uplift other than counter. And here location of counters is in a short distance from the starting point based on the destination. Thus, this study hypothesizes that one stop service and waiting time have a significant influence on both satisfaction and loyalty.

Hypothesis 9: One stop service (OSS) has a positive effect on satisfaction;

Hypothesis 10: One stop service (OSS) has a positive effect on loyalty;

Hypothesis 11: Waiting time (WT) has a positive effect on satisfaction;

Hypothesis 12: Waiting time (WT) has a positive effect on loyalty.

Satisfaction and Loyalty

Satisfaction is treated as an emotion based feeling or a degree of pleasure and contentment or a distance between performance and expectations in service (Bloemer and Kasper, 1995; Andreassen and Lindestad, 1998; Cronin, Brady, and Hult, 2000; Dick and Basu, 1994; Fornell et.al., 1996). Satisfied customers have a higher price tolerance for their preference and had less attraction for switching to competitors (Fornell et.al., 1996). Several studies have confirmed a direct positive relationship between satisfaction and loyalty (Andreassen and Lindestad, 1998; Bloemer and Kasper, 1995; Butcher, 2001; Cronin et.al., 2000; Dick and Basu, 1994; Fornell et.al., 1996; Hellier, 2003; Stank et.al., 1999; Ostrowski, O'Brien, and Gordon, 1993;) with the assumption that switching cost increases the intention of customer loyalty (Jones, Mothersbaugh, and Beatty, 2000; Lee and Cunningham, 2001). Therefore, it is hypothesized that satisfaction is a significant predictor of loyalty.

Hypothesis 13: Satisfaction has a positive effect on loyalty.

Methodology

The objective of the research is to examine the relationships among predictors and criterion variable particularly on transport sector of Bangladesh. The perception survey questionnaire measured through earlier suggested measures opined by the researchers/experts and also changes

made by states using a five-point closed order Likert scale, where 1 indicates that the variable is not important at all and 5 is very important with extensive support from the literature. The sample size was targeted 450 initially, but 405 were selected based on avoiding missing responses.

Conceptual model

Based on the literature review, the hypothesis and measurement model formulated for the exogenous variable and the endogenous variables as shown in figure-1 to explain the relationship among the factors of passenger transport services on satisfaction and loyalty.

Figure-1: Theoretical model of the study

Data Analysis

To assess direct relationships among the studied variables the researcher has performed confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988). SPSS 22 and AMOS 22 had been used to perform these analyses. These analyses supposed to help to understand which model fits the data best while presenting a credible assessment on the antecedents of loyalty of passenger transport services of Bangladesh.

Result

Statistical techniques were applied to assess the reliability and validity of the survey and to obtain more clarity regarding the influence of the selected variables on satisfaction and loyalty.

a) Reliability

In measuring reliability coefficient for the different construct were computed using the reliability procedure in SPSS 22. The reliabilities of the entire construct used in this study found to be above the standard set which is 0.70 (Nunnally, 1978). The range of Cronbach's alpha shows the reliability of the variables of research ranges from $\alpha = 0.711$ to $\alpha = 0.781$; mean scores had been computed by equally weighting the mean scores of all the relevant to each construct.

b) Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Confirmatory factor analysis was used here to measure the construct validity of the model whereas convergent validity is for existence of construct determined by the correlations exhibited by independent measures of the construct. To assess convergent validity the loading estimates and construct reliability were investigated. In AMOS 22, convergent validity can be measured using the measurement model by determining the significant value of each item's estimated pattern coefficient on its posited underlying construct factor (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988).

To measure the uni-dimensionality, convergent and discriminant validity through AMOS 22, the CFA provides overall fit indices ($\chi^2 = 32.971$), chi-square degrees of freedom = 15, RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Estimation) = 0.026, GFI (Goodness of Fit Indices) = 0.947, AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Indices) = 0.923, CFI (Comparative Fit Indices) = 0.959, and NNFI (Non-normed Fit Indices) = 0.962.

Here Goodness-of-fit of the final model indicated 'reasonable or good fit' or RMSEA = 0.026. It is suggested that $0.05 < \text{RMSEA} < 0.08$ is for good fit (Hair et.al, 2006). In this study, CFI = 0.959 demonstrate reasonable fit. A rule of thumb for the CFI and the incremental indexes is that values greater than roughly 0.90 may indicate reasonably good fit of the researcher model (Hu and Bentler, 1999). GFI = 1.0 refers to perfect fit (Joreskog & Sorbom, 1999). Therefore, a GFI = 0.947 indicates reasonably good fit if the researcher's model in this study. The AGFI of 0.923 indicates reasonably good fit of the researcher

model. The NNFI (Non-normed Fit Indices) or Tucker-Lewis Index has been recommended a value of 0.90 or better for good fit (Bentler & Bonett, 1980; Hair et.al., 2006). Thus, an NNFI = 0.962 for this study implies good fit. From the above goodness-of-fit evaluation, confirmatory factor analysis for the final measurement model reasonably supported the model's fit.

Measurement Model:

a) Structural Equation Model (SEM)

A structural model is fit to the data according to the model structure given in the figure-1. All the paths are assessed to find significant positive standardized path coefficients. The goodness of fit indices for the final structure model, shown in the bottom part of table-1, suggests a good fit to the data: small ratio of chi-square to degree of freedom (<2), great values of GFI, AGFI, CFI, NFI (>0.9) and RMSEA values (<0.05).

Table 1 : Goodness-of-fit results of the study

Goodness-of-fit statistics		Values	Desired range of values for a good fit
Chi-square test	χ^2	32.971	
Degrees of freedom	Df	15	≥ 0
Chi-square/ degrees of freedom ration	χ^2/df	2.19	2 to 5
Goodness of fit index	GFI	0.947	> 0.90
Root mean square error of approximation	RMSEA	0.026	< 0.08
Incremental fit measures Adjusted good-of-fit index	AGFI	0.923	> 0.90
Tucker-Lewis Index	TLI	0.962	> 0.90
Comparative fit index	CFI	0.959	>0.95
Normed fit index	NFI	0.939	> 0.90

Table-2: Standardized Regression Weights:

			Estimate
Satisfaction	<---	In	.335
Loyalty	<---	In	.132
Satisfaction	<---	Pr	.084
Loyalty	<---	Pr	.224
Satisfaction	<---	QS	.173
Loyalty	<---	QS	.224
Satisfaction	<---	BrB	.296
Loyalty	<---	BrB	.331
Satisfaction	<---	OSS	.218
Loyalty	<---	OSS	.123
Satisfaction	<---	WT	.436
Loyalty	<---	WT	.328
Loyalty	<---	Satisfaction	.250

Figure-2: Standardized estimates

In accordance with the parameter estimates shown in figure 2 and table 2, all the factors have positive effect on both satisfaction and loyalty and these findings are proposed in H₁ to H₁₂. The analysis results also yield that satisfaction related positively and significantly with loyalty and this finding proposed in H₁₃.

Table # 3: Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results:

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Satisfaction	<---	In	.299	.046	6.510	***	
Loyalty	<---	In	.101	.038	2.664	.008	
Satisfaction	<---	Pr	.070	.043	2.632	.008	

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Loyalty	<---	Pr	.161	.032	4.956	***	
Satisfaction	<---	QS	.160	.047	3.374	***	
Loyalty	<---	QS	.176	.036	4.847	***	
Satisfaction	<---	BrB	.253	.044	5.756	***	
Loyalty	<---	BrB	.241	.035	6.811	***	
Satisfaction	<---	OSS	.189	.045	4.242	***	
Loyalty	<---	OSS	.091	.035	2.613	.009	
Satisfaction	<---	WT	.388	.046	8.490	***	
Loyalty	<---	WT	.249	.040	6.253	***	
Loyalty	<---	Satisfaction	.213	.053	4.028	***	

Note: S.E. = Standard error; C.R. = Critical ratio, *p < 0.01

b) The Hypothesized Casual Structure Model

As shown in table 3, the regression weight of income to satisfaction ($t=6.510$; $p < 0.05$); income to loyalty ($t=2.664$; $p < 0.05$); price to satisfaction ($t= 2.632$; $p < 0.05$); price to loyalty ($t=4.956$; $p < 0.05$); quality service to satisfaction ($t=3.374$; $p < 0.05$); quality service to loyalty ($t=4.847$; $p < 0.05$); brand belief to satisfaction ($t=5.756$; $p < 0.05$); brand belief to loyalty ($t=6.811$; $p < 0.05$); one stop service to satisfaction ($t=4.242$; $p < 0.05$); one stop service to loyalty ($t=2.613$; $p < 0.05$); waiting time to satisfaction ($t=8.490$; $p < 0.05$); waiting time to loyalty ($t=6.253$; $p < 0.05$); satisfaction to loyalty ($t=4.028$; $p < 0.05$) were significant. This indicated that the factors had significant direct effect on satisfaction & loyalty, and satisfaction had direct effect on loyalty.

The estimation results in table 3 indicate that the thirteen hypotheses, H_1 (Income to Satisfaction), H_2 (Income to Loyalty), H_3 (Price to Satisfaction), H_4 (Price to Loyalty), H_5 (Quality Service to Satisfaction), H_6 (Quality Service to Loyalty), H_7 (Brand Belief to Satisfaction), H_8 (Brand Belief to Loyalty), H_9 (One Stop Service to Satisfaction), H_{10} (One Stop Service to Loyalty), H_{11} (Waiting Time to Satisfaction), H_{12} (Waiting Time to Loyalty), and H_{13} (Satisfaction to Loyalty) are

supported, with path coefficients of 0.299, 0.101, 0.070, 0.161, 0.160, 0.176, 0.253, 0.241, 0.189, 0.091, 0.388, 0.249, and 0.213 respectively.

Discussion

The transport and travel services of Bangladesh provide service variety in context to the varying nature of demand and buying power. The customers prone to quality service at a fair cost are tremendously wanting. Though the study covered only a specific region with limited number of samples, the intensity of customers toward the brand is not negligible. The maximum factors affecting both the satisfaction and loyalty were brand belief, one stop service, quality service and waiting time to get the added advantage for the Starline services. Basically, the other travel services are not consistent based on continuity and regularity. On the other hand, personal needs educate customers on ways the service addresses their needs. Perceived service alternatives are used to aware of competitive offerings and addressed to match appropriately with needs. The brand belief or reputations of Starline in this area is sky top for longer service tenure.

In fact, company's reputation generally described as a combination of the stakeholders' assessments between company's earlier role and how well the company's general performances coping with the social and political environment (Logsdon & Wood, 2002). Finally, self - perceived service roles educate customers to understand their roles and how to perform better. In order to predict travel behavior, it is important to understand how individual characteristics of a person interact with the characteristics of the situation, therefore understanding the positive and negative evaluative factors influencing destination choices of the people are worth considerable (March & Woodside, 2006; Laws, 1995; Holloway, 2004). For intercity bus carrier to get a competitive advantage, effective marketing strategies has the key role players to endure in the long-distance transportation market whereas loyalty worked as a measure (Flavian, 2001). Though the study focused the loyalty on the existing and previously considered for travel services, but this loyalty preference is also influential to potential customers by advocacy, resistance to change and relative preference of the brand in competition (Butcher, Sparks, and O'Callaghan, 2001).

In addition, the findings of this study provide meaningful insights into the evolving dynamics of passenger travel preferences and loyalty reflecting a broader shift in consumer behavior, where psychological and emotional dimensions of trust, credibility, and brand association significantly affect decision-making. Interestingly, the study underscores that brand belief can outweigh purely functional considerations such as cost efficiency or travel time, which contrasts with earlier research that primarily emphasized service quality and affordability as the dominant factors. This

new dimension of loyalty demonstrates that passengers in the Feni–Chittagong route are not merely consumers of a travel service but active stakeholders who seek a holistic and reassuring travel experience. Such preferences highlight the necessity for transport service providers to go beyond conventional service improvements and foster deeper engagement strategies through branding, consistency, and value-driven communication. Moreover, the supported hypotheses regarding the relationships between loyalty, satisfaction, and influencing factors reaffirm that passenger well-being is multi-dimensional. It is not confined to tangible aspects like cleanliness or accessibility alone but extends to the intangible perception of trust in service providers. The strong path coefficients observed in this study indicate that transport services can secure long-term competitive advantages by strengthening brand positioning while maintaining operational efficiency.

Conclusion

The study highlights that passengers' loyalty and satisfaction in travel services are influenced not only by traditional factors such as price, waiting time, and service quality, but also by deeper considerations like brand belief and perceived flexibility. However, findings confirm that these determinants play a critical role in shaping travel choices on the Feni–Chittagong route, with brand trust emerging as a strong driver of loyalty. This indicates a shift in passenger mindset, where emotional connection with a service brand becomes as important as tangible service features. Ultimately, the results provide transport operators with valuable insights to strengthen competitive positioning by enhancing service quality, building brand credibility, and ensuring passenger-centered experiences. In reality, the factors imposed to be a monopoly business concern in this territory particularly on passenger travel service by quality service. The trust achieved by the brand and one stop service got unique psychological positioning among the customers. The future researcher can justify the situation with more sample size and identify such situation in other regions of the country. The situation is one-way alarming for monopoly business concern being chances to deteriorate services in the long run and prospective investment option on the other side.

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